

TOPONYMS AS A FACTOR OF PATRIOTIC EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of toponymic material as a source of linguistic studies. In our opinion, the appeal to this material revitalizes students' interest in the subject and broadens the students' general outlook.*

Keywords: *toponym, microtoponymy, linguistic studies, cognitive interest, humanization of education, linguistic observation.*

One of the most important elements of local history work is the study of toponyms, names of geographical objects. It serves as a means of stimulating interest in the study of the past and present of one's region by searching for links between the geographical conditions of the area, history, the language of the people and their reflection in geographical names. As you know, the most important stages of the history of the material and spiritual culture of the people are reflected in the toponymic vocabulary.

This lexical material is a valuable source of knowledge of the history of the language and culture of the people. Toponymy serves as a means of stimulating cognitive interest in the study of the past and present of one's region by searching for connections between the geographical conditions of the area, history, the language of the people and their reflection in geographical names. Undoubtedly, this material also arouses great interest among students.

Toponymy is part of the national vision of the world, as geographical names conceal both the wisdom of the people and historical traditions. Local toponymy is the name of cities, villages, settlements, streets, squares, alleys. These are names that are continuously connected with the natural features and historical past of the region, with the names of outstanding personalities.

You can start a toponymic study of native places by collecting well-known names of streets, squares, alleys of our city or its individual microdistricts, neighborhoods of villages, rivers and streams, lakes, ravines. The totality of names of this type is defined as microtoponymy (from Greek. "micro" - small plus "toponym" - the name of the place) of the city. This layer of vocabulary contains valuable and rich information about the history of the city itself and its modern life, and at the same time, which is very important, about the Russian language and its history.

The appeal to this particular material is due to various reasons. Microtoponymic vocabulary, like all toponyms in general, attracts attention with its accessibility, which makes it possible to use it as an object of linguistic and local history work already in elementary school. L. Uspensky in the book "The Riddles of Toponymy" writes that "toponyms are not subject to any fluctuations. There is always a harvest on them. They don't hide or run away. Go to them, they are waiting for you" [Uspensky: 1976, 266].

Microtoponymic material is represented by the names surrounding us since childhood. Microtoponyms are quite accessible to observation, classification. The result of the work may be the compilation of a dictionary of regional microtoponyms, which will reflect the old and new street names of the hometown. It is microtoponyms that are living witnesses of the historical past and present of the native land, expressed by means of language. In the process of research, it is possible to consider the functioning, meaning and origin of microtoponymic vocabulary, the

development and change in time of certain names. Deciphering such names makes it possible to restore the historical past of the native land.

Thus, microtoponyms perform the function of focusing historical and linguistic memory. This has become especially relevant recently, when many streets of our city are being renamed and old historical names are being returned. The system of working with local toponymic material arouses the constant interest of students, developing the desire to expand their knowledge. Fosters a sense of patriotism. In addition, they acquire skills in dealing with dictionaries, reference books, get acquainted with toponymic terms that are completely new to them. Using regional material in the process of teaching Russian language, in particular microtoponyms, will contribute to the enrichment and activation of the dictionary, the development of speech, interest in the native language, in the native land, will allow you to learn to see the unusual in the ordinary, the amazing in the inconspicuous. Such work will contribute to the preservation of the traditions of a particular district, region and, therefore, will make it possible to solve not only educational tasks, but also to educate patriots of your country and your region.

The first source of familiarization with local toponyms is a visual overview of the modern process of functioning and interaction of mimes in people's everyday speech. Both old toponyms and new formations are observed here. Next, visual observations are compared with the reflection of the toponymic situation on the map and atlas.

Toponymic research is carried out directly on the studied area, as well as on detailed topographic maps, atlases, both modern and historical. Terrain features, in most cases, give rise to toponyms-oronyms – that is, the names of terrain features (ravines, hills). Sources and springs, including those not indicated on maps, also have their own names, even if they are appellatives – that is, common names used as proper names. The maps show the official names of streets and alleys, but they also have unofficial names that are known only within a certain territory. This also needs to be taken into account and noted. Often, the lines of narrow-gauge, intra-territorial, factory railways are not even graphically reflected on general maps and diagrams. These objects, in turn, can also be assigned folk names. The maps also do not reflect folk microtoponyms, which are of great importance in everyday communication. The most detailed maps do not reflect the names of detached buildings (shops, residential buildings, etc.), small groves, gardens, separately growing trees, small playgrounds, etc.

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Thus, linguistics is a part of the regional component, which may include other elements, and a particularly significant part that contributes to the implementation of many modern principles of updating the content of education, primarily the humanization of education. The appeal to this material revives the interest of students in the subject, promotes the activation of the thought process, forms linguistic observation, expands horizons. Therefore, the content of teaching students the Russian language should include the toponymic space of the modern language.

REFERENCES

1. <https://scienceforum.ru/2015/article/2015016184#:>.
2. Barandeev, A.V. History of geographical names. Russkaya toponimiya v terminakh [Russian toponymy in terms], A.V. БарандеевBarandeev, Moscow: Librokom Publ.Либроком, 2014, 320 p.
3. Degtyarev, V. N. BEEL LA RUS. Secrets of ancient toponyms / V. N. Degtyarev, S. A. Trachymenok. - Moscow: Belye alvy, 2013. - 304 p.
4. Jaxon, T. HN. Austr i gordum. Drevnerusskiye toponymy v drevneskandinavskikh istochnikakh [Old Russian toponyms in ДжаксонOld Norse sources].
5. Jaxon, T.HN. Austr i gordum. Drevnerusskiye toponymy v drevneskandinavskikh istochnikakh [Old Russian toponyms in ДжаксонOld Norse sources].
6. Russell, Jessie Renaming of Turkic toponyms in Armenia / Jessie Russell. - Moscow: VSD